

Synthesis and characterization of *N*-substituted benzimidazole derivatives and study of their antibacterial and antifungal activity

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Abstract : *N*-(4-(1*H*-Benzo[*d*]imidazol-1-yl)phenyl)-3-nitrobenzamide, *N*-(4-(1*H*-benzo[*d*]imidazol-1-yl)phenyl)-4-chlorobenzamide, 4-(1*H*-benzo[*d*]imidazol-1-yl)benzenamine and *N*-(4-(1*H*-benzo[*d*]imidazol-1-yl)phenyl)-4-bromobenzamide were synthesized and characterized by IR and NMR techniques. These *N*-substituted benzimidazole derivatives were screened for their antibacterial activity by Well diffusion method against *Bacillus subtilis* (*B. subtilis*), *Staphylococcus aureus* (*S. aureus*) (Gram-positive) and *Escherichia coli* (*E. coli*), *Klebsiella* (Gram-negative) bacterial strains. The compounds tested were found to have good antibacterial activity against all bacteria. The antifungal activity of the compounds was tested against *Aspergillus flavus* (*A. flavus*) and *Aspergillus niger* (*A. niger*) fungal strains. Antifungal results indicated that 4-(1*H*-benzo[*d*]imidazol-1-yl)benzenamine and *N*-(4-(1*H*-benzo[*d*]imidazol-1-yl)phenyl)-4-bromobenzamide derivatives showed better activity than the reference drug.

Keywords : Benzimidazole, EDC, HOBT, antibacterial, antifungal.

Introduction

Benzimidazole is a benzene fused with imidazole heterocyclic compound found in nature as *N*-ribosyl-dimethylbenzimidazole, which serves as an axial ligand for cobalt in vitamin B₁₂¹. An imidazole nucleus in the benzimidazole molecule has made it a versatile heterocycle with wide spectrum of biological activity, such as in antiulcer, antiviral, antifungal and anticancer². Benzimidazole moiety is a structural motif of naturally occurring nucleotides, therefore it finds application as a drug scaffold in the medicinal chemistry^{3,4}, for cytotoxicity and antiviral activity against a panel of RNA and DNA viruses⁵. 5-Nitrosubstituted and 2-phenylsubstituted benzimidazole derivatives have shown best result. This could be because of the improved binding on viral proteins through hydrogen bonds formation which may result in π -interactions between the electron deficient rings of the drug⁶. Hence we for the first time, report the synthesis of various *N*-substituted benzimidazoles and their antibacterial and antifungal activities.

Experimental

Materials :

Benzimidazole, 1-fluoro-4-nitrobenzene, 1-ethyl-3-(3-dimethylaminopropyl)carbodiimide hydrochloride (EDC.HCl), *N,N*-diisopropylethylamine (DIPEA) and hydroxybenzotriazole (HOBT) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich and solvents such as *N,N*-dimethylformamide, tetrahydrofuran (THF), methanol (MeOH) and dichloromethane (DCM) were purchased from S. D. Fine Chemicals. Thin layer chromatography (TLC) was conducted on aluminium sheets coated with silica gel 60 F obtained from Merck, with visualization by UV lamp (254 or 360 nm). ¹H NMR spectra were recorded with a Bruker AVANCE 400 MHz instrument at 25 °C. IR spectra were recorded in Perkin-Elmer Spectrum-1 instrument with freshly dried KBr pellets in the range between 4000–400 cm⁻¹. Antibacterial activity of these compounds were checked against *B. subtilis*, *S. aureus* (Gram-positive) and *E. coli*, *Klebsiella* (Gram-negative) bacterial strains using Well diffusion method. Ampicillin (20 μ g) was used

as a reference standard for antibacterial study. The anti-fungal activity of these compounds was tested against *A. flavus* and *A. niger* fungal strains using amphotericin (20 µg) as standard.

Experimental protocol :

Scheme 1. Synthesis of *N*-substituted benzimidazole derivatives.

Synthesis of 1-(4-nitrophenyl)-1H-benzo[d]imidazole (1) :

1-Fluoro-4-nitrobenzene (0.0169 mol, 1.78 ml) was added to a solution of benzimidazole (0.0084 mol, 5.79 g) in dry DMF (20 ml). The above mixture was treated with anhydrous K_2CO_3 and refluxed for 6 h. The completion of the reaction was monitored by TLC. After completion the reaction mixture was poured into water to get a yellow coloured solid. The solid yellow product was filtered under vacuum. The product was yellow in colour. Yield 92%; 1H NMR ($CDCl_3$) : 6.722–6.740 (2H, d, CH), 7.208–7.278 (6H, m, CH), 7.428–7.409 (1H, d, CH), 7.708–7.689 (1H, d, CH), 8.299 (1H, s, CH); ^{13}C NMR ($CDCl_3$) : 110.38, 120.59, 121.66, 122.66, 123.87, 124.90, 128.57, 129.20.

Synthesis of 4-(1H-benzo[d]imidazol-1-yl)benzenamine (2) :

Ammonium chloride (0.0334 mol, 1.8 g) dissolved in water was added to the solution of 1-(4-nitrophenyl)-1H-benzo[d]imidazole (0.00334 mol, 0.8 g) in THF (10 ml) : methanol (4 ml) followed by iron powder (0.0267 mol, 1.5 g) and refluxed for 3 h. The completion of the reaction was monitored by TLC. The solvent THF : methanol was removed under vacuum. The remaining residue was dissolved in ethyl acetate and filtered under vacuum to remove the Fe powder. The crude product was purified through column chromatography using silica gel 60–120 and hexane : EtOAc solvent system. The obtained product was colourless oily liquid. Yield 90%; 1H NMR

($CDCl_3$) : 5.362 (1H, s, NH_2), 6.722–6.740 (2H, d, CH), 7.206–7.278 (6H, m, CH), 7.409–7.428 (1H, d, CH), 7.689–7.708 (1H, d, CH), 8.299 (1H, s, CH); ^{13}C NMR ($CDCl_3$) : 110.30, 121.16, 123.68, 123.75, 124.62, 125.84, 132.82, 141.70, 144.39, 146.57.

General procedure for the synthesis target compounds (3a-c) :

Synthesis of *N*-(4-(1H-benzo[d]imidazol-1-yl)phenyl)-4-chlorobenzamide : EDC.HCl (0.001435 mol, 0.274 g), HOBt (0.001554 mol, 0.210 g) and DIPEA (0.00239 mol, 0.308 g) was added to the solution of 4-(1H-benzo[d]imidazol-1-yl)benzenamine (0.00119 mol, 0.250 g) in DMF (5 ml). To this mixture, 4-chlorobenzoic acid (0.001315 mol, 0.205 g) was added and stirred at room temperature for 24 h. After completion of the reaction the reaction mixture was poured into water and extracted with EtOAc. The organic layer was dried with sodium sulphate and the crude product was purified through column chromatography using silica gel 60–120 using hexane : EtOAc solvent system. IR (KBr) 3086.11 (amine), 2922.16 (C-H), 1681.93 (C=O), 1604.77 (C=C), 1325.10 (N-H), 734.88 (-Cl) cm^{-1} . *N*-(4-(1H-Benzo[d]imidazol-1-yl)phenyl)3-nitrobenzamide : IR (KBr) : 3317.56 (amine, asym), 3068.75 (amine, sym), 2854.65 (C-H), 1685.43 (C=O), 1616.68 (C=C), 1417.68 (N=O), 1360.17 (N-H) cm^{-1} .

Results and discussion

N-Arylation reaction of benzimidazole with 1-fluoro-4-nitrobenzene was carried out with potassium carbonate in DMF. The resulted compound 1-(4-nitrophenyl)-1H-benzo[d]imidazole (1) was further reduced with iron/ammonium chloride in order to get 4-(1H-benzo[d]imidazol-1-yl)aniline (2). The products 1 and 2 were confirmed by

Fig. 1. Antibacterial (A and B) and antifungal activity (C and D).

Table 1. Antibacterial and antifungal activity of the synthesized benzimidazole derivatives

Derivatives	Bacteria	Zone of inhibition		Fungus	Zone of
		10 µg/ml	20 µg/ml		inhibition
					30 µg/ml
3a	<i>S. aureus</i>	25 mm	34 mm	<i>A. niger</i>	10 mm
3b		30 mm	44 mm		8 mm
3c		4 mm	6 mm		7 mm
2	<i>B. subtilis</i>	30 mm	40 mm	<i>A. flavus</i>	11 mm
3a		25 mm	31 mm		11 mm
3b		21 mm	28 mm		–
3c		8 mm	12 mm		11 mm
2	<i>E. coli</i>	30 mm	39 mm	<i>Aspergillus fumigatus</i>	14 mm
3a		25 mm	36 mm		18 mm
3b		25 mm	40 mm		17 mm
3c		26 mm	38 mm		11 mm
2		30 mm	45 mm		16 mm
3a	<i>Klebsilla</i>	31 mm	38 mm	–	–
3b		35 mm	40 mm		–
3c		20 mm	27 mm		–
2		29 mm	36 mm		–

the IR and ^1H and ^{13}C NMR analysis. The new *N*-substituted benzimidazole derivatives were synthesized in good to excellent yields by a simple coupling procedure involving EDC.HCl and HOBt. EDC.HCl is a carbodiimide used to activate carboxylic acid towards amide or ester formation. Hydroxybenzotriazole (HOBt) was mainly used to suppress racemisation and improved the efficiency of peptide synthesis⁷. *N,N*-Diisopropylethyl amine (DIPEA) was used as a base. All the final compounds were analysed with IR spectra.

The synthesized compounds 4-(1*H*-benzo[*d*]imidazol-1-yl)benzenamine (**2**), *N*-(4-(1*H*-benzo[*d*]imidazol-1-

yl)phenyl)-4-bromobenzamide (**3a**), *N*-(4-(1*H*-benzo[*d*]imidazol-1-yl)phenyl)-4-chlorobenzamide (**3b**) and *N*-(4-(1*H*-benzo[*d*]imidazol-1-yl)phenyl)-3-nitrobenzamide (**3c**) were screened for their antibacterial activity against *B. subtilis*, *S. aureus* (Gram-positive) and *E. coli*, *Klebsiella* (Gram-negative) bacterial strains. The initial screening of the synthesized benzimidazole derivatives have shown to be active against both Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria. These compounds showed positive results in the *in vitro* antibacterial studies against *E. coli* and *S. aureus* strains. *In vitro* antifungal activity against *A. flavus*, *Aspergillus fumigatus* and *A. niger* strains were also checked. The results of the antibacterial and antifungal activity are shown in Table 1. The compounds tested were found to have good antibacterial activity against all bacteria. Antifungal results indicated that some of the derivatives possessed a broad spectrum of activity against tested fungi.

Conclusion

In summary, four *N*-substituted benzimidazole derivatives were synthesized and characterized with IR and NMR techniques. These *N*-substituted benzimidazole derivatives showed good antibacterial activity in the initial screening. They are active against both Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria. They also have good antifungal activity against *A. niger*, *A. flavus* and *A. fumigates*.

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